

Catalyzing Responsible Assessment for Open Science

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Abstract. This poster presents the DORA Practical Guide to Implementing Responsible Research Assessment at RPOs (2025), highlighting its actionable strategies for aligning research assessment with Open Science (OS) principles. It offers practical approaches to recognize diverse contributions, ensure transparency, and foster inclusive, community-driven evaluation practices in line with global RRA initiatives that advance OS.

Conference Themes: Transparency and Inclusivity of Assessment Processes, Recognition of Contributions to Open Science

Keywords: responsible research assessment, DORA, implementation, practical guide, research performing organizations.

1 Main Contribution

The DORA Practical Guide to Implementing Responsible Research Assessment at Research Performing Organizations (RPOs)[1], published in May 2025, provides actionable guidance for transforming research assessment practices. This poster links Open Science (OS) to the Guide’s key assessment activities and moments, offering strategic support for those aiming to implement Responsible Research Assessment (RRA) in their institutions.

The Guide directly supports the GraspOS conference’s core themes by offering practical pathways for RPOs to foster open, transparent, and inclusive assessment systems:

- **Recognizing contributions to OS:** The Guide broadens the scope of assessment beyond traditional publications, explicitly valuing diverse outputs such as datasets, software, public engagement, and policy work. It encourages incentives for openly shared, discoverable, and reusable outputs. Narrative CVs are promoted to capture non-traditional and OS-related contributions, with an emphasis on quality over quantity.
- **Ensuring transparency and inclusivity:** The Guide advocates for clear, fair, and open criteria in assessment processes. It supports qualitative, expert-led evaluations, complemented by responsible use of metrics. Practical tips address implementation challenges, including bias mitigation and training for assessment committees. Co-creation with research communities is emphasized to build trust and accountability.

By translating RRA principles into concrete steps, the Guide addresses the critical “how-to” gap in implementation—similar to the GraspOS SCOPE+i Framework. It

aligns with global initiatives such as CoARA[2], the Barcelona Declaration[3], and the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science[4], reinforcing a coordinated movement toward more holistic and equitable research evaluation.

The Guide’s novelty lies in its focus on implementation. It shifts the conversation from why RRA is needed to how it can be achieved in practice. It outlines nine key activities and targeted interventions for pivotal assessment moments. Its design as a dynamic, evolving resource—featuring real-world examples and community feedback—underscores its practical utility. With a strong emphasis on adaptability and co-creation, the Guide recognizes that no one-size-fits-all solution exists, making it a vital tool for RPOs committed to advancing OS through responsible assessment.

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